

THE PECULIARITIES OF THE TRANSLATION OF PROVERBS AND SAYINGS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF A.QODIRIY'S WORK "THE SCORPION FROM THE ALTAR")

Aqila Shabonqizi Sattorova

Teacher, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

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Annotation

This article analyzes the peculiarities encountered in the process of translating proverbs and sayings. In particular, on the example of A. Qodiriy's work "The Scorpion from the Altar", how national and artistic means of expression are reflected in the translation is studied. The original and translated texts are compared, and semantic and stylistic changes are analyzed. The translator's methods of rendering folk expressions are also considered. The article emphasizes the importance of the correct reflection of proverbs and sayings in translation.

Keywords: proverbs and sayings, artistic translation, A. Qodiriy, "The Scorpion from the Altar", national expression, translation methods, folk proverbs, linguistic features, literary analysis.

Introduction: The art of translation is one of the important areas of literature and linguistics, which is of incomparable importance in conveying the culture, traditions, spiritual and mental world of a particular people to other languages. In particular, in the translation of works of art, preserving the national color, correctly conveying the author's style, and naturally expressing images and events are among the important issues. In this regard, the process of translating examples of folk oral creativity, including proverbs and sayings, is of particular importance.

Proverbs are the product of centuries-old experience, life views and wisdom of the people, and they express the worldview of the people in a short and concise form. Therefore, their translation is not limited only to changing the means of language, but also requires conveying the mentality of a particular people through other means of language. Therefore, the translation of proverbs is considered one of the most difficult and responsible processes for the translator. Translating them word for word can often lead to logical or stylistic errors. The translation requires taking into account the phraseological units, artistic means and cultural context of both languages.

The novel "The Scorpion from the Altar" by one of the prominent figures of Uzbek literature, Abdulla Qodiriy, is one of the finest works of 20th-century

Uzbek prose, in which folk expressions, proverbs and sayings are widely used. This increases the national spirit and artistic value of the work. This article analyzes how proverbs and sayings are reflected in various translations of the work. It studies whether they are translated correctly or incorrectly, whether the author's style is preserved, and the peculiarities allowed in the translation process.

Main part: Although some proverbs can be translated directly, most proverbs are artistically incompatible or their meaning may change. Since proverbs are related to the lifestyle and customs of a particular people, it is important to express them in a way that is understandable to representatives of other cultures during the translation process. In many cases, proverbs that are similar in meaning can be found in other languages. However, in some cases, if an equivalent proverb cannot be found, the translator is forced to express its meaning in a free form.

As an example, let's consider the following proverbs from the novel "The Scorpion from the Altar", for example:

"A thief starts first from his home"

This proverb is one of the Uzbek folk wisdoms, the meaning of which is that a person who starts a bad deed first harms those around him. If translated literally, this phrase may not be understandable in another language. For example, if translated directly into English as "A thief starts from his own home", it may cause misunderstanding. Therefore, it is advisable to adapt it to the existing English proverb "Charity begins at home, but so does sin"

"There is no sickle - reap the wheat with your hands"

This proverb means that in a certain situation it is necessary to solve the problem in an alternative way. It can be directly translated into Russian as "Нет серпа - жни пшеницу руками". However, this expression is not widely used in Russian. Therefore, it is appropriate to adapt it to the Russian proverb "На безрыбье и рак - рыба" (Where there is no fish, even a crab is a fish).

"El oq'ziga elak tutib bo'lmaydi"

This proverb means that people cannot stop talking, any talk will spread anyway. The corresponding proverb in English could be "You cannot stop people from talking" or "Rumors spread like wildfire".

A. Qodiriy used proverbs and sayings extensively in his novel. It is important to analyze how these proverbs have changed in different translations of the work. Sometimes a direct translation of the proverb is used, but this is not always understandable or natural. Some proverbs are replaced with an analogue

that is suitable for the culture and language of another language. While preserving the main meaning of the proverb, it is adapted to the style of the target language.

For example, let's take the proverb "If you pet someone else's dog, it will bite you." It can be directly translated into English as "If you pet someone else's dog, it will bite you," but this does not sound natural. The English equivalent is "No good deed goes unpunished." Proverbs and sayings are the historical and cultural memory of the people, and care must be taken when translating them. In the translations of the novel "The Scorpion from the Altar" there are cases of changing proverbs or directly translating them. In order to preserve the artistic spirit of the original, the translator must try not to lose the national flavor. Therefore, it is effective to search for equivalent proverbs or use the method of free translation in translation.

The translation of proverbs and sayings is one of the most complex and important aspects of literary translation, requiring the translator's skill, deep knowledge of the language and culture. Since they reflect the national mindset, historical experience and wisdom of the people, not only the literal meaning, but also their artistic and aesthetic value should be preserved in the translation process.

Abdulla Qodiriy's novel "The Scorpion from the Altar" is one of the most artistically mature works of Uzbek literature, in which folk proverbs and sayings are widely used. These proverbs play an important role in naturalizing the general style of the work, the speech of the characters and conveying the national color. In the process of translating them, the translator uses various methods - word-for-word translation, searching for equivalent proverbs or free translation. Each approach has its own advantages and disadvantages, but the most important aspect is that the translator must express proverbs and sayings in another language in the spirit and meaning inherent in the Uzbek people.

The analyzed translations show that literal translation is not always effective. Because the language and culture of each nation are different, phraseological units from one language can lose their meaning or become ambiguous when translated into another. Therefore, translators should use the methods of searching for analogical equivalent proverbs or free translation. For example, translating the proverb "El og'ziga elak tutib bo'lmayda" into English as "Rumors spread like wildfire" will more accurately convey its meaning. Also, preserving the national flavor and artistic style is very important in translation. Since A. Qodiriy's style is written in a lively, folk language, the translator must

preserve the tone of speech along with its content. Artistically incorrect translations can change the tone of a work, make characters' speech seem artificial, or reduce the aesthetic impact of the work.

In conclusion, the translation of proverbs and sayings is not only a linguistic process, but also a cultural mediation. The translator must convey not only the words, but also the historical and cultural context behind them. The example of the translation of proverbs in the novel “The Scorpion from the Altar” shows that effective translation should be based on conveying the meaning and spirit, not the literal meaning. This, in turn, requires the translator’s creative approach, linguistic knowledge, and intercultural thinking.

References:

1. Kasimova, S. S. (2024). Transformation of phrases and its destructions. *Salud, Ciencia Y Tecnología - Serie De Conferencias*, 3, 740. <https://doi.org/10.56294/sctconf2024740>
2. M.R.Abdullayeva and others. Social Psychological Features of the Process of Professional Stress in Pedagogical Activity // *Journal Power System Technology* ISSN: 1000- 3673, V 48, Issue 4. 2024/12. Pages 3325-3334
3. Sayed Mohamed Ahmed Korayem, Sharustam Giyasovich Shamusarov, Gulnora Sattorovna Mutalova, Buzakhro Marufjanovna Begmatova, Nargiza Makhmudovna Saidova. Calling for the Use of Intermediate Language in Teaching Arabic to Non-Native Speakers, Its Foundations and Problems // *Power System Texnology Journal*, ISSN: 1000-3673 issue 48 (2024), -pp 2221-2236.
4. Xayrulla Khudoyorovich Khamidov, Ikrom Yusupovich Bultakov, Karima Saydanovna Raxmanberdiyeva, Sarvinoz Sayfullayevna Kasimova, Shirin Baxtiyarovna Sodiqova. Linguistic Expertise of Educational Literature: Analysis and Results // *Journal Power System Technology*. Vol. 48 No. 4/2024 p. 4017-4027. <https://powertechjournal.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1253>
5. Sattarovna, M. G. (2023, November). ON THE ISSUE OF DEFINING NEWS TEXT. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 158-163).
6. Begmatova B. M., Mutalova G. S., Kasimova S. S. The Direct Object And Its Use In Arabic Language // *Boletin de Literatura Oral-The Literary Journal*. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 1. – C. 3601-3609.
7. Bakhadirova D. PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATION OF ARTISTIC WORKS (BASED ON THE WORKS OF A. NAVOI) // *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE*. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 273-277.

8. Bekmuratova S., Matchanova F., Musinova Z. THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE LIFE OF GIRLS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 5 (Special Issue). – С. 336-338.
9. Lafasov, U. P. (2023). ABDALLAH QADIRI'S NOVELS USING THE METHOD OF METONYMY. SPAST Abstracts, 2(02).
10. Bekmuratova S. Linguocultural features of proverbs on the topic of patriotism in the Uzbek and English languages //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1-3.
11. Lafasov, U. P. (2022). BASICS OF LANGUAGE SCIENCE AMONG UZBEKS. Oriental Journal of Education, 9-12.
12. Lafasov, U. P. (2021, December). THE HARMONY OF WORDS AND IMAGES IN THE WORK OF ABDULLAH QADIRI. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 98-101).

